

**THE IMPORTANCE OF READING CULTURE IN THE
SOCIALIZATION OF THE INDIVIDUAL****Oygul Dulanboeva****Researcher of the National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek, PhD in Sociology
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17941869>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 11th December 2025Accepted: 12th December 2025Online: 13th December 2025**KEYWORDS***reading culture, socialization,
personality, social function, role,
status, society, text.***ABSTRACT**

This article examines the importance of reading culture and the ability to comprehend written texts in the process of an individual's socialization. At the same time, attention is given to the socialization process itself, its various stages, and its distinctive characteristics. In addition, the article analyzes views and theories on the individual and their cultural development within the framework of socio-philosophical disciplines. Particular emphasis is placed on a detailed analysis of sociological theories that explain the role of reading in the process of individual socialization.

Human development is a complex process that pursues two main goals—economic and social development, that is, the enhancement of people's capabilities and potential. The growth of individuals' abilities and capacities, in turn, creates opportunities for the overall development of society, the state, and each citizen. In other words, people represent the main productive resource, as well as the foundation for the creation of material and spiritual wealth and the provision of social services. Therefore, expanding access to education and raising it to the level of societal demand, along with fostering a healthy and well-developed new generation, constitutes one of the most urgent tasks of the present time. Only under such conditions can a mature individual become a reliable pillar of democratic and profound economic transformations.

In this regard, most researchers identify three key aspects of human development:

- economic integration of society;
- social protection of the population;
- financial support for public education and cultural institutions, as well as the development of long-term strategic plans for their future [1; 2; 3].

Every society produces an individual appropriate to its own nature, just as the individual does not remain indifferent to the emergence and development of that society [4]. At the same time, a person possesses the ability to influence and appropriate the surrounding environment. This influence is not realized through aimless or blind activity. By understanding the laws of society and the conditions of one's own life, and through purposeful practical activity, an individual begins to transform the social environment. A person is not merely a product of circumstances and history, but also their creator. In the historical process, the degree of active participation, initiative, and determination of the masses—especially young people—largely depends on the consciousness, responsibility,

diligence, and creative initiative of working individuals as creators of material and spiritual values [5].

The study of the subject whose role is crucial in the phenomenon of reading is particularly important in researching the formation of reading culture. According to scholars who have examined reading processes on a scientific basis, the subject of reading is the individual. In particular, N. A. Rubakin argued that the true content of self-education lies not in the book itself, but in the individual [3]. He emphasized that within a bibliological system, the primary criterion for evaluating any book is the individual, just as all elements of human history revolve around the person as their central point.

The individual, as a bearer of social relations, constitutes one of the central concepts of sociology. Without studying the individual, it is impossible to resolve any sociological problem. Philosophical and psychological theories developed in the late nineteenth and twentieth centuries exerted a strong influence on the formation of sociological conceptions of the individual [6].

Based on traditional philosophical theories, the concept of the “individual” is interpreted in several ways:

- as a being created by nature, God, or society, who should primarily recognize and adapt to their given existence;
- as an infinitely active creator capable of transforming their way of life and consciously shaping their own existence;
- as a subject who forms themselves through object-oriented activity, with development dependent on the external objective world.

In psychology, the individual is understood as a set of mental traits, processes, and relationships that distinguish one subject from another. From a psychological perspective, individuals differ in their capacities due to unique innate and acquired characteristics. Individuality reflects the irreproducibility of biological and social traits, transforming a person into an active participant within a group or community.

Although these ideas influenced the sociological understanding of the individual, sociology employs its own conceptual framework. In a broad sense, sociology defines the individual as a set of social characteristics inherent to a human being, formed through social development and active participation in social relations via communication and activity.

Sociological approaches to the individual can be divided into two major groups: macrosociological and microsociological theories. Macrosociology views the individual as a product of society–culture, history, and environment—a perspective evident in the works of É. Durkheim, M. Weber, and T. Parsons. These theorists emphasize the process of socialization, defined as the assimilation of societal culture, norms, values, ideas, behavioral rules, and cognitive stereotypes [7]. Through socialization, individuals develop not only socially adaptive qualities but also mechanisms of social reflexivity and activity.

In contrast, microsociology focuses on interpersonal relations, emphasizing the importance of roles and status in the socialization process. From this perspective, an individual’s integration into various social groups and structures is shaped by their social position and functions.

Thus, in studying the phenomenon of reading, it is essential to examine both the overall development of the individual and their purposeful professional growth in a coherent and integrated manner. According to J. Reykowski, the core of the social mechanism of personality development lies in individuals' awareness of themselves as part of society [8]. This awareness is based on two key processes: individuation and identification. Individuation forms the distinction between "self" and "others," while identification dissolves boundaries, shaping a sense of similarity and belonging.

Consequently, the individual develops through the interaction of individuation and identification. Some cultural values promote individuation, while others contribute to identification. As a social being, a person becomes an individual through social relations shaped by technological, moral, and cultural development. By contributing to social history and transforming social relations, a human being becomes a fully developed individual.

In conclusion, the formation of a mature individual in society is determined by two interrelated processes: the harmonization of social relations imposed by society and the individual's active creation of social relations within that society. Personal relations encompass economic, social-political, and cultural interactions assimilated across all spheres of life. These relations, formed within the social environment, manifest in an individual's aspiration toward comprehensive development. It is precisely this inner drive that motivates engagement in reading and continuous self-development.

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